

A Single-Source-Of-Truth for Future Ship Life-Cycle Data

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Abstract

During the last decade the author have been in contact with diverse attempts from the academia (theoretical) and industry (practical) to implement a single-source-of-true for the ship design value chain. This paper compiles some impressions from these attempts, motivated by the existing SEUS EU project on smart shipbuilding, that NTNU and 7 other partners are part of. The paper starts with a discussion on the concept of single source of truth in ship design for closing the ship life cycle loop. This is followed by the idea of database and dashboards able to aggregate six data domains in a unique and coherent structure. The advanced but fragmented present situation of information silos in maritime is exemplified via selected approaches in design, construction and operation. The final section presents a speculation for the future, in which standardization can be driven by the government and/or market, as well as a promising exercise in using LLM for handling event-driven sources of truth.

1. Single Source of Truth in Ship Design, Construction and Operation

The need to study the concept of single source of truth (SSoT) in ship design value chain is currently fomented by the Smart European Shipbuilding EU project (SEUS - seus-project.eu) that the author coordinates. The project aims to develop a digital platform that enhances the efficiency of shipyards by integrating design and management software. Add to it previous experience in industrial research projects aimed at similar data coherence during conceptual ship design for re-use in consequently lifecycle phases, *Keane et al. (2017)*, *Gaspar (2018)*. Moreover, other recent initiatives linked to close the loop from operational to design enhanced the importance of a coherent database all over the lifecycle, closing the loop between operation and design, *Taylor et al. (2024)*, *Gaspar and Bekker (2025)*.

Fig.1: Single source of truth for the ship lifecycle data

SSoT is this here understood here as data, knowledge, information and wisdom (DIKW) from the main activities expected in the ship design value chain, as observed in Fig.1: concepts, CAD/CAE engineering documents, ERP and CAM systems, compliance with classification societies, assembly operations, sea trial, performance validation, operation under diverse mission profiles, monitoring and sensors, emissions compliance, MRO, retrofit and end of life towards recycle.

Note that the discussion of the idea and importance of a unified database for maritime activities is as old as the initial digital implementations from the 1970s. *Wolanyk's (1979)* essay from the 6th Research and Engineering for Automation and Productivity in Shipbuilding Symposium (REAPS) reads as well now as in 1979: “We raised the question of why should a corporation consider their own database (...). To be able to retrieve information and know that it is the most accurate and up to date available. Other reasons are to reduce data redundancy and thereby permit sharing of data among applications and allow data usage restrictions to be applied effectively. Knowing where the data is located, or that it resides in fewer locations, makes it easier to control that data. Finally of course, maintenance of data integrity and data independence issues can be addressed. By data independence issues we mean the ability to change a program or to change a database and not have to change the other, concluding with (...) there are no database management system packages commercially available today that really suit both the commercial and the manufacturing side of an organization as well as the engineering side. However, there is a commonality between the two application areas that should be tied together, perhaps, through interface systems. The second conclusion is that the effort involved in the implementation of a data dictionary is worth it to put the shipyard in position to take advantage of new technology.”

Two distinctive SSoT concepts are here analysed. The first, within an organization, as mentioned by Wolanyk, and currently advertised and implemented in diverse maritime companies. In this way, a clear boundary of data ownership is traced. When within a design office, for instance, SSoT would mean access to existing and previous designs; within a shipyard, construction drawings and suppliers' information from delivered ships; from shipowners, operational data and maintenance schedule. The second concept follows the lifecycle of the ship itself, aggregating data from many different stakeholders of the life cycle phases and ownership, within a single coherent database.

It is my belief that the majority of the academic articles and industrial sales pitch focus on big promises connected to the second concept, while justifying the existing challenges to achieve it in the lack of the first one in place. In other words: “We can have the whole digital twin of the ship ready to be accessed, including design, construction and operation, but first you need to implement X, Y and Z in your company... as soon as all other stakeholders do the same, the solution is implemented”. The catch is that tools and methods X, Y and Z vary to each service provider, and in reality, we introduce new digital processes in top of existing ones, masking (and increasing) the real fragmentation.

Keane et. al. (2017) correctly points that a solution for the integration challenge may be use of PLM as umbrella, as a basis for emergent technology. The authors also add the criticism that modern PLM fails in the promise to handle multi-taxonomy/disciplinarily issues. In reality, modern PLM systems yet require a semi-fixed hierarchization of the ship design products, system and process, not much different in theory as the SFI group system from the pre-digital era. Such need constrains the understanding of the system by a specific set of rules, which may not work in a different context of market, construction or operation.

To exemplify this challenge, we can use the good explanation of *Semini et. al. (2018)* for the four core strategies that larger ship design firms have when detailing and constructing the vessels, Fig.2. A more detail description of each strategy is observed in *Bronson and Gaspar (2024)*.

A coherent data architecture for strategy I, where the upstream phases are within the same boundaries, can be achieved, as all the decisions have similar context around them, such as regulations, incentives and best-practices. When third parties from other countries enter in the process, such as the cases of strategies II to IV, then the chance that a coherent unified model can exist when managed by multiple stakeholders is close to none. There is a large market of digital engineering conversion in countries like Poland, Romania, Ukraine and Turkey, in which naval architecture offices are contracted to translate the data send from the designer office and supplier towards the modus operandi of the ship yard. The same hull, with the same basic design drawings, will require organization to different taxonomies to be constructed in Norway, Turkey or China.

Semini et al. conducted studies on the different strategies employed in Europe, particularly in Norway. They found that although there are still some shipyards that fully construct a ship locally, the most common strategies include offshoring the entire hull construction and or blocks abroad.

Fig.2: Shipbuilding Strategies, from Bronson and Gaspar (2024), based on Semini et al. (2018)

The rest of this paper will discuss some of the reasons for this to happen, with an overview of the six key data domains that seems to have the largest importance. Later, an overview of selected existing solutions for coherent database that are being used for design, construction and operation. The proposition for the future of SSoT starts with reminiscences of the past, with the realization that some of the issues raise more than 45 years ago are yet a reality. A brief discussion on event-driven source of truth is then presented, biased by past attempts and current research that the author was/is involved. The role of the invisible hand of the market, or visible hand of the governmental entities is discussed, based on examples from the building industry and the successful implementation of BIM in the last years. The paper closes with some speculation about the role of AI in developing and managing a SSoT and the importance of openness, transparency and traceability.

2. Data Domains and Dashboards – Taxonomies that matter and Path Dictionaries

The challenge in stablishing a SSoT for the maritime sector lies in its high level of customization within a narrow margin to accept risks. As recently summarized by Yilmaz et al. (2025), maritime industry fits the profile of project based firms, Gann and Salter (2000), in which design and production processes are organized around highly customized solutions, operating with volatile stakeholders in their value chain. Such concept matches well Erikstad's (1996) seven aspects preliminary ship design, namely: one of kind, multi-dimensional performance evaluation, high cost of error, shallow knowledge structure, strong domain tradition, complex mapping between form and function and stricter time resources and constraints.

Motivated by the lack of mature discussion on the effects of the disruption from upstream to downstream phases for the maritime systems' digital models, Bronson et al. (2024) compiled four existing gaps towards developing a common data platform in the maritime industry: Lack of Open Standards, Non-standardized Data Models, Non-integrated pipeline and Lack of Adoption Strategies. Such gaps are commonly understood as the reason why the maritime industry lacks a common taxonomy able to parse Fig.1 data into a structure that can be accessed and exchanged between the many actors.

One of the attempts of the existing activities of the SEUS project is to investigate which data domains are the more relevant to be considered when gathering and organizing lifecycle data. We converged to six domains, namely: Process, Product, Systems (Functional), Geolocation, People and Contextual (market, rules, regulations). Central to the idea of domains includes the fact that they are highly linked,

and information falling within one domain can be reinterpreted to other domains based on intent and function. Fig.3 presents a mock-up of what could be a dashboard to access these domains during design and construction, *Bronson and Gaspar (2024)*.

Fig.3: Mock-up of a dashboard incorporating the six domains in a unique and coherent structure for the ship design lifecycle, first sketched in *Bronson and Gaspar (2024)*

As an aggregator, the concept from Fig.3 would be acting as a central repository, what in the past could also be called a “data dictionary”. This would store the relevant required definition and metadata in a unique location, while the detailed information would be located in an existing silo. In other words, a dashboard with paths to reach more detailed data about a certain element, filtered by tasks, user (people), location, systems and lifecycle phase.

Note that the concept here is not the same as a unified software platform solution, such as PLM, ERM, ERP or CAD/CAE platforms, neither a fleet performance monitoring software. The dashboard

resonates with the idea of aggregators already used by the building industry, such as Synchro 4D, screenshot presented in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Synchro 4D construction management platform (bentley.com/software/synchro/)

Rather than competing with state-of-the-art tools such as CAD suites and project management solutions, such aggregator (or federated model) uses the standardization of building information modelling (BIM) and its .IFC standard widely used in the European building industry. IFC files generated by many actors within different phases of the project are visualized under the same umbrella, with an adequate GUI that facilitates data exploration in diverse important domains, such as:

- Temporal: with an interactive timeline of the phase of the project and the correspondent status of the product, visualized in 3D.
- Activities: with ownership, duration and the connection with the completion of a part of the product of service from a supplier.
- Human, with the persons and service providers performing the work.
- Resources, with a unified list of supplier and raw materials, connected to physical and economic data.
- Links and relations, that is, a hierarchization of the process connected to requirement and criteria that must be achieved in a certain order.
- Gates, milestones and checkpoints.
- Breakdown of the system, with subsystem, components and traceability of ownership.

Coherence in the data taxonomy means having access of the information in a way that it can be accessed, aggregated and re-arranged according to the needs. Fig.3 is not a proposal for a new digital platform suite or new industrial standard, in the same way that the software from Fig.4 is not a CAD, project management or BIM software. Both used the idea of open and accessible data format to generate an interactive and visual compilation of the data domains until now, heavily making use of the timeline and how the other product varies of the time. In the following section we exemplify the concept based on existing practices in design, construction and operation.

3. Silos and current SSoT attempts in Ship Design, Construction & Operation

There is no doubt that we achieved a high level of digitalization and formalization of difficult and complex ship design, construction and operation tasks within an information silo. Independently, each of us has their own way of organizing information in a way that we can access and re-use. Within small groups the gain in productivity and performance is also well established, especially when the department is able to handle tasks of a singular discipline (e.g. CAD for classification compliance, or outfitting). The users (people domain) usually share the same ontology of the task, that is, a set of concepts and categories in a subject area or domain, as well as the relations between their field of work and the external world.

Within different domains and lifecycle phases, however, the challenges discussed in *Gaspar (2018)* seem yet to be valid, as the integration and flexibility promised by modern SSoT systems are not yet delivered in everyday activities. Among its reasons, the cost for purchasing and training users among the life cycle activities in engineering and yard, especially in strategies with work made abroad, Fig.2, seems to play an important role. Other reasons are: limited freedom to customize libraries and adequate tacit knowledge and local procedures to the data standard; additional development cost for customization, macros and APIs able to handle the uniqueness of each company; high cost to acquire, install, train personal and keep servers running; risk of being locked to a system, and losing independence if features and licenses terms changes.

The sales pitch and training materials of computation tools for the maritime usually avoids presenting workarounds that may suggest the use of a competitor tool for a complimentary task, ignoring that experienced professionals have different preferences on how to solve the problem complex problem, and that a certain methodology proposed by the software *X* may not be the most effective among the users. Note that this is not a new problem. *Knapp (1980)* presents a discussion in similar tone on the challenges of firstly implementing digital planning in shipbuilding: "(...) the speed of the computer has been harnessed to increase the overall document volume generated by the Planning department, but the sophistication of the software is not being utilized. Instead, the yard's traditional planning techniques are being dropped, with no improved methodologies replacing them. Moreover, the overall experience levels of the planners is on the decline (...) Planning "to suit Production" is replaced with planning "to suit the computer", with the overall approach tending away from the shipbuilding process. (...) No computer software system has been created which understands all of the intricacies of the shipbuilding process, contrary to the assumptions of some planners". I believe that the same is yet true not only in construction, and changing the substantive above for design or operation seems to work well.

In the following, this is exemplified based on my personal experience, and any criticism should not be directed to maritime companies or software developments, as it serves only to illustrate a challenge that has been acknowledged for decades.

Design: Hull design and file formats, related to additional work to convert existing data from *silo A* in the format/tool used by *silo B*. As example, the use of diverse CAD tools and files to handle the hull and GA. While there are plenty of unified solutions to design, analyse and detail the hull shape and properties, in reality large and serious ship design companies do have high skilled employees spending time in the conversion of models between the disciplines.

Personally, I have been exposed to at least four similar cases in which Rhinoceros is used for the main conceptual design and overall arrangement in the pre-contract phase, shared by engineering and sales, in medium and large European ship design companies, different countries. In all these cases, the companies had access to a complete solution to handle hull design and analyses, such as CADMATIC, NAPA or FORAN/SIEMENS NX, usually used by the structural and hydro engineers. The process goes something like this (my bias): the chief design has a personal collection of previous designs and constructed projects in Rhinoceros, with a very detailed 3D arrangement of the hull, as well as macros to export the concept to fancy 3D renders and architecture-like isometric GAs. Added to it a well calibrated spreadsheet, parametrized to match the Rhinoceros catalogue, fed with decades of data from

previous analyses, towing tank experiments and sea trial data. In this way, a new design could be balanced quickly with interpolation of the existing data, with a precision good enough to assure the client that it is functional. After contract, this Rhinoceros project is then shared with the other departments for compliance, sometimes abroad. The same hull would then be converted to match stability calculations (e.g. NAPA or SARC), structural analyses (e.g. DNV) and seakeeping. Changes would need to be fed back to Rhinoceros, as to keep the sales model updated. Only after the hull is properly balanced that the Rhinoceros model is thus abandoned and the detailed engineering of subsystems is then carried out in the software of choice, as well as the CAD for classification and construction.

Fig.5: Attempt of balanced conceptual design using Rhinoceros, *Suhas (2023)*

Suhas (2023) touches this topic, attempting to reinvent the wheel into Rhinoceros, as to achieve the initial design balance with scripts via the Grasshopper functionality. His work exemplifies well the advantage of modern CAD software in empower designs to create something unique, and later quickly parametrize right into the 3D environment, while the reality of extremely complexity of introducing in such tools a niche analyses, such as stability and structural compliance, Fig.5. The work shows an impressive compilation of scripts and basic naval architecture procedures for a container vessel. The use for real analyses and compliance, however, is not achieved as the amount of code and interaction grows much faster, as the real number of activities within stability and structural compliance does not allow it to be done by a single person.

Another lesson to be adapted from the Lincoln et al. (1980) discussion from, in relation to the economics of implementing digital tools. The authors conclude from many implementation experiences that “whether it makes sense to use computers in shipyard production control is simply a question of economics, namely, whether the savings from increased control more than cover the cost of the system and provide a reasonable rate of return (...) Generally speaking, for small shops with fewer than 100-200 active jobs at any given time, a well-thought-out manual system is probably the most cost-effective.

Beyond this point automated systems become economically attractive”. Again, thinking in terms of design activities, the manual work of the main designer in the CAD tool of her preference (e.g. Rhinoceros) fits well the speech. When, however, the number of tasks raises to include the stability and structural engineering, the manual work should include automation, which in our examples can be translated as the seamless data exchange between different software.

Construction: Product and processes management. The second example is connected to classical connection between the product realization, that is the construction of the ship, and the management of the activities, including personal and supply chain logistics. Again, we do have amazing complete solutions to handle both activities separately. A suit like CADMATIC, for instance, is able to handle a large database of components and assemblies with millions of elements in 3D for the outfitting and ship systems (e.g. HVAC). On the other hand, shipyards have in house planning tools able to store information about building blocks division, workshop planning and stock with control of the information via the supply chain. Communication between these both sides, yet falls in the same conversion work commented in the first case, as the yard has usually a different taxonomy to organize it the ship than the engineering. The first is based on WBS process and resources availability, in a tight schedule balancing use of existing resources and warehouse management. The second is thought in terms of functionalities and technical compliance, in which divisions do not necessarily follows a *physical* constrain.

Fig.6: CADMATIC eShare, handling functional and product structures within the 3D platform

An existing service to tackle this problem is here exemplified by CADMATIC eShare tool, Fig.6, in which the system allows the handling of functional breakdown, exemplified by the SFI code, at the same time that the WBS process, exemplified by the ERP functionality and purchase number.

Operation and Digital Twins: The DT concept did not gain enough momentum to be considered a lucrative part of the business, and become a feature, that is, good to have when it really kicks off. The full loop integration aimed at Fig.1 is yet to be achieved. That said, assuming the stabilization of the hype for digital twins (DT), lets briefly look into solutions that are already available in the market able handling operational data in at least three different silos: Design companies, analyses and monitoring and emissions compliance.

As stand-alone solution, one example is Blue Ctrl, a subsidiary of Ulstein group, which offers software to integrate diverse marine systems control and monitoring, such as power and energy management systems, in a single umbrella, as to future initiatives of automation and remote control for efficient performance during operation. It promises collection of data (onboard) and data analyses (on land) as

decision support towards reduced fuel consumption, automated reporting, predictive maintenance, monitoring of third-party equipment and fleet comparison (ulstein.com/companies/blue-ctrl-as). Fig.7 exemplifies the services, and presents a screenshot of a possible dashboard for a grid support unit.

Fig.7: Blue Ctrl services (left) and dashboard example (right) for operational monitoring.

CADMATIC also presented its eShare solution for digital twin readiness, as the detailed ship model presented in Fig.6 can be connected via APIs to live data monitoring, e.g. from a tank measurement, Fig.8 left, *Seppälä (2019)*, or valve pressure. Recent material from the company indicates that they are extending DT functionalities towards live monitoring of more complex ship activities.

Fig.8: CADMATIC eShare DT features for a tank level gauge (left) pressure indicator (right)

Lastly, we dig into environmental compliance and shipping activities. EU has ratified concrete measures to achieve its strategy in the form of the Fit for 55 policy package. Two of the most impactful regulations targeting commercial transport vessels are the extension of the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) to maritime transport in January 2024 and FuelEU Maritime in January 2025. The framework in practice indicates that services will be offered to maritime companies (shipowners and charters) towards supporting vessel energy performance and decarbonisation.

Fig.9: DNV Emissions Connect Service, *Hermundsgård (2025)*

As usually the level of data ownership is not equal in the portfolio of shipping management companies, mixing own vessels fleet while providing services to third parties, the common point of shared data ends up being low granularity electronic log books, such as noon reports. The same DT hype is pushing some changes in this area, given the more rigorous expected compliance for the EU policies. Fig.9 exemplifies DNV approach in this direction, with screenshot of the Emissions Connect service, a platform to monitor and manage emissions data from voyage to fleet, generating and sharing required emissions statements for compliance with EU ETS and FuelEU, *Hermundsgård (2025)*.

Another aggregator of operational data that has been *appearing in the radar* is exemplified by the portfolio Navtor web-based tool, Fig.10, such as the digital log books, Fig.10 (left), ship/fleet emissions reports, Fig.10 (centre), and even online auditing that enables playback of VDR data, navigation audits, and investigations within a unique dashboard, Fig.10 (right).

Fig.10: Navtor web-based tools for aggregating operational data

4. Speculations for the Future: (in)visible hand and AI

Some speculation for the future has already been spoiled in this article with the general idea of a closed loop from Fig.1 and the attempts to develop a mock-up of a useful aggregator in Fig.3. I assume that this discussion managed to convey the message about a) the importance of a coherent SSoT database, not necessarily in terms of size and features, but in terms of properly represent digitally and act upon real activities from design, construction and operation; b) the extensive toolbox of commercial software that we have are extremely useful in their silos, but not yet not able to handle the differences of domain and actors, exemplified by the digital systems illustrated in Figs.5-10. It is certain that we are heading towards more aggregated and unified solutions than a decade ago.

Mandatory BIM for public investments in Europe

Fig.11: BIM requirements in Europe, compiled by *Mitera-Kielbasa and Zima (2024)*

There are at least two actors that could affect the existing SSoT scenario, which worth the exercise of speculation: the role governmental agencies and AI. Firstly, the visible hand of the governmental agencies and its impact on the invisible hand of maritime market behaviour. Actions such as emissions compliance can lead to an uniformization of data regardless software providers of classification society of choice. Such effect was observed in the building industry, with the growing of BIM and .IFC data in the last decade, exemplified in Fig.4. This phenomenon was undoubtedly influenced by diverse EU

government mandates the use of BIM in public procurement, in a recent review, compiled in Fig.11, *Mitera-Kielbasa and Zima (2024)*.

The real utility of AI and the current hype of LLM may actually be harvested if we combine the openness of the data a path, in which we are able to use event-store and event-source techniques. Again, such approaches are older than me, with a discussion of event-based planning made by Knapp (1980), concluding that summarization should be prioritized over detailing (my emphasis): “consider a ship requiring 2000 major erection activities, printed at 50 lines per page (...) to properly complete the picture (...) add in 200 Engineering drawing related activities, 500 material tracking activities, 200 major test items, and 4000 shop support activities. The total number of activities has grown to 6900 (...) Output volume is not the only problem concerning the analysis of the plans and schedules. All too often, software packages are deemed best if they present every detail of the data. While detail is necessary, data summarization is required to assist both Planning and Management with a comprehensive overview of the yard's load and problem areas.”

To test and exemplify this context in light of a modern event-drive source of truth, it was developed a very simple mock-up for fleet data regarding orders. Such database of all events was then fed to current AI online tools (free version Gemini 2.0). in which the software was successfully able to filter and extract basic reasoning, in a huma friendly way different than existing filtering menus observed in CAD, PLM and spreadsheets. As someone usually pessimistic about the use AI in maritime applications, this was positive surprise, motivating the author (and hopefully the reader) to investigate deeper the possibility of a common and unified event-driven SSoT platform able to handle the cradle-to-cradle loop presented in Fig.1.

Fig.12: Simple event-driven aggregator, with querying handled by commercial LLM

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